

A Probabilistic Approach to Structural Health Monitoring of Composite Aircraft Nacelles: Implementation and Validation

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ABSTRACT

The present work aims to assess the implementation of an embedded structural health monitoring (SHM) system enabling condition-based maintenance of composite aircraft nacelles. It describes the complete process from the choice of the active elements to the implementation of the SHM strategy by means of elastic waves on an A380 nacelle and analysis of the results obtained after experimentation on substructures with actual size before the flight test campaign. Some critical aspects are also discussed such as temperature compensation, probability of detection, anisotropy and the maturation process that led to the validation of the proposed SHM algorithm. Some recommendations are made for future in service implementation of SHM techniques.

1. INTRODUCTION

Recent years have witnessed a growing interest in the field of smart structures. Smart structures are advanced structures with self-capabilities that are emerging as a promising way to improve the intrinsic and extrinsic characteristics and to entail innovations beyond the ingenious design of final products. Ongoing programs on their development opens fascinating new frontiers for applied research and engineering products. For aircraft industries, they have come up with the concept of Multifunctional Aircraft Structure (MAS). The principle is to take advantage of new materials to integrate airframe structure with functional systems [1]. The structure can respond to changes due to environmental conditions and to perform a number of tasks such as Transmit/Receive (T/R) function, structural enhancements and repairs, Conformal Load-Bearing Antenna Structure (CLAS) and Structural Health Management (SHM).

On MAS aeronautical structures, SHM and its related technologies is the main form of smartness that is studied. It is a broad field encompassing many synergetic technologies that provide together automated systems whose purposes are to identify and characterize possible damage, in real-time or at specified time intervals, within structures [2]. SHM is the key technology to enable the transition from schedule-driven maintenance to condition-based maintenance. It's a system-level technology which integrates sensors/actuator networks with structures, software to interpret sensor signals, and hardware to process and manage the signals [3], its maturity based upon the complexity and targeted solutions can be classified into four different sequential levels [4] : detection, identification, quantification, and prognosis. SHM involves multidisciplinary fields ranging from material, structure, signal processing, data mining, fracture mechanics, fatigue life analysis and more. It aims to detect, localize and evaluate the severity of damages.

Because of its multilayer structure, composite materials are inherently suitable to host smart materials. However, fiber reinforced materials are more complex. Their structural anisotropy and the fact that they contain different phases of material (fibers and matrix) generally result in various types of damage with different propagation characteristics. Damage detection and determination of the remaining strength and life of the structure remains a challenging task. To date, most service life predictions are based on measurements of damage indicators (DI) and their growth towards criticality or failure, e.g. fatigue crack length, material loss due to corrosion or wear, etc... However, the dissemination of instrumentation technologies, complex structures, harsh environments and operational variability render many of the proposed SHM methods difficult to provide reliable condition-based maintenance decisions for in-service structures. Moreover, despite more than two decades of research on SHM systems, the results are still largely academic, due to difficulties to transport results from the laboratory to real systems.

Figure 1: Aircraft nacelle

An engine nacelle (Figure 1) is a highly integrated system. It brings together a full range of technologies and meets technical, ecological and economic requirements of aircraft manufacturers, engine producers and operating airlines. The nacelles are a critical part of an aircraft, as they perform multiple functions. They are at the interface between the plane and the engine. Indeed, the nacelles optimize the internal and external air flows towards the propulsion system and protect it against any exterior damage. They contribute to the braking of the plane on the landing, and to its aesthetic aspect. They also reduce noise emissions and all this in drastically severe conditions as extreme temperatures $[-50^{\circ}\text{C} + 120^{\circ}\text{C}]$, pressure and dimension constraints, whilst remaining as light as possible. New nacelles tend to be lighter, quieter, smarter and more electric. The development of SHM for aircraft composite structures is thus a necessary trend in the case of nacelles subject to strong environmental constraints. Several SHM methodologies have already been developed for this purpose. They involve guided elastic waves [5], with piezoelectric elements as sensors/actuators.

Figure 2: Complete SHM Framework

The aim of the present work is to assess the implementation of an SHM process for an actual aircraft nacelle. It describes the complete process (Figure 2) from the choice of the active elements (PZT) and their placement [6] to the implementation of the SHM strategy (based on Lamb waves [5]) on an A380 nacelle and analysis of the results obtained after experiments on sub-structures with actual size and flight tests. To cope with operational variability and complexity of the structures, we propose to provide a metric helping the condition-based maintenance decisions for in-service structures. This is possible by capturing a part of the effect of environmental variability and using a Bayesian framework for damage detection and localization. This will represent the probability of how likely are SHM system outputs. Some critical aspects are also discussed such as temperature compensation, probability of detection [7], anisotropy and the maturation process that led to the validation of the proposed SHM algorithm [8]. Some recommendations are made for future in service implementation of SHM techniques.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the validation of the structures-glue-piezoelectric elements and the PZT self-diagnosis procedures. Section 3 presents the robust probabilistic detection and localization algorithm. The substructures and flight test results are given in sections 4 and 5 respectively.

2. VALIDATION OF THE COMBINATION "HOST STRUCTURES-GLUE-PIEZOELECTRIC ELEMENTS" AND PZT SELF-DIAGNOSIS

Before being able to work with any SHM systems based on piezoelectric active elements, their integration and specifically their bonding should be validated with respects to the host structures environmental conditions. To do so, electromechanical (EM) signature techniques have raised a real interest in the structural health monitoring community (see for example [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6]). The EM signature technique consists in measuring the EM signature of a piezoelectric element which is surface-mounted on a host structure in order to pinpoint incipient damages that may appear on the structure (damage detection) or to detect any damage on the sensor itself (sensor diagnostics). We are here particularly interested in detecting damage that can potentially occur on the sensor as a result of thermal or mechanical load.

2.1. Tested specimens with glued piezo-electric elements under harsh environment

The specimens to be used in the present study are those representatives of the nacelle. Two components are of particular interest in the present work: the fan cowl outer panel made of monolithic carbon-fiber-reinforced polymer composites, and the inner fixed structure made of aluminum honeycomb core sandwich panels with carbon-fiber-reinforced polymer composites skins. Thus, two kinds of specimens with dimensions $400mm \times 300mm \times 31.4mm$ ($L \times l \times h$) have been tested: sandwich specimens (Figure 2) and monolithic specimens (Figure 4a)

Furthermore, there exist two main technologies of piezoelectric elements that can be used for SHM purposes: rigid ones (PZT) and flexible ones (MFC). To validate the use of both types of elements, each specimen has been equipped with both. The PZTs provided by Noliac are disc units while the MFCs provided by Smart Materials have a rectangular shape (Figure 3).

PZT disc from NOLIAC

MFC patch from SMART-MATERIALS

Figure 3: PZT and MFC elements

The glue that has been tested in this study and has been applied under pressure with use of vacuum bags is the Redux 322, a modified epoxy film adhesive able to operate from - 55 °C to 175 °C.

2.2. Laboratory simulation of the thermal and mechanical environment

The nacelle structure is subject to external solicitations including thermal and mechanical environmental flight conditions outside the aircraft and in the vicinity of the engine. Thermal load can be expressed in terms of temperature values ranging from $T_1 = -50^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $T_2 = 100^{\circ}\text{C}$. Mechanical loads correspond to the sizing of the host parts and thus to the allowable of respective materials. In the context of bond assembly deformation compatibility, these conditions are to be expressed in terms of maximum strain magnitude ϵ , of order 10^{-3} . In order to validate a given SGP system, the observation of its response to these conditions is to be carried out in laboratory conditions.

Mechanical loads are applied by conventional testing tensile/compressive machines: when the substrate strain is positive, the load is applied by means of a classical tensile test. For inducing negative strains, flexural tests are used. The size of the specimens is chosen at least double with respect to the specimens in order to avoid the influence of the samples boundary on the deformation of the assembly. Thermal loads are applied in a climatic chamber simultaneously with mechanical load when mounting configuration allows enough room for the chamber or separately when not possible. For monolithic specimens, tensile loads (Figure 4a) are representative of the kind of mechanical load they are exposed to, and sandwich specimens undergo compressive loads as they mainly endure this type of solicitation during flights.

Figure 4: (a) Monolithic specimen equipped with MFC elements under tensile and flexural load of a sandwich specimen at -60°C . (b) Functional plates with 5 PZT elements

2.3. Piezoelectric elements self-diagnostic

Sensor self-diagnostic procedures have been developed to be able to detect any damage occurring on the piezoelectric elements itself. Such procedures are based on the measurement of the electromechanical admittance of the piezoelectric element from which its static capacity is being extracted. This static capacity is afterward used as an indicator of debonding or failure of the piezoelectric element under study. This procedure has already been used to detect experimentally debonding and damages appearing on piezoelectric elements [9,10,11,12,13,14]. This procedure has also already been used in aeronautical and spatial contexts [15,16,17].

A healthy piezoelectric element well bonded to its host structure will exhibit a static capacity given by

$$C_c = \frac{S}{t} \times \epsilon_{33} \times [1 - \kappa^2] \quad (1)$$

where S and t are the surface and the width of the considered element, ϵ_{33} its dielectric permittivity and κ^2 stands for the electromechanical coupling coefficient of the piezoelectric element and ranges between 0 and 1. Hence, any damage in the piezoelectric element or its debonding from the hosted structure will manifest itself whether as a diminution of its usable surface S or of its dielectric coefficient ϵ_{33} . Now

by choosing a suitable threshold on the variation of the slope of this static capacity (Figure 5), a decision can be made on the integrity of the PZT elements before performing the SHM system.

Figure 5: PZT elements self-diagnostic by monitoring the slope of the static capacity ($Y(\omega) = i\omega C_c$).

3. ROBUST DAMAGE DETECTION AND LOCALIZATION

SHM has been the topic of extensive research efforts over the last thirty years. This technology is now progressing toward operational service and several different techniques that depend on the structure's material, on the technology used for acting and sensing, on the position, size, and the nature of damage may be employed. Among others, we can highlight vibration based approaches [18,19] and more specifically the wave-based approaches that have the advantage to be sensitive to small flaws and offers the capability to monitor significant areas with few sensors [20]. We used in this work a robust active SHM strategy that deals with environmental and operational variability. The approach is based on the Time of flight of elastic wave propagation [5]. Time of flight is defined as the time lag between incident wave that the sensor first captures and the wave scattered by damage that the same sensor subsequently captures.

3.1. Probabilistic damage detection

Damage detection is generally achieved by comparing features extracted from signals of the structure at healthy and damaged states [4]. This comparison is achieved by means of damage sensitive features, which are commonly referred to as Damage Indexes (DIs). The most commonly used DIs are constructed from the difference or the ratio between the signals measured in the healthy and damaged states. The decision regarding the presence or not of the damage is usually taken in a statistical framework, which requires repeating the measurement of signals on the structure a lot of times in order to build distributions associated with the DIs, from which a decision threshold is found. In order to design a SHM detector, thus two issues have to be solved. The first one is the choice of the Damage Index (DI) to consider and the second one is the way to use it for detection purposes. A detector design thus does not reside solely in the DI choice and implementation but also includes the processing steps needed to compute a reliable decision threshold using the available DIs [21]. This decision threshold has to be determined according to a trade-off between two probabilities (Figure 6): POD (probability of detection) and PFA (probability of false alarm). PFA represents the probability to detect a damage when the structure is healthy - $P(Detection|Healthy)$ wherea POD represents the probability to detect a damage when the structure is faulty or damaged - $P(Detection|Faulty)$. Airline business models rely on PFA as the main performance criteria [22]. In general, due to the high safety level, the requirement on PFA is 10^{-9} which is very small. In order to determine the decision threshold under such constraint, a first approach consists in estimating the probability density of the DIs in the healthy state and to work with this estimate. In this case, parametric and nonparametric density estimation methods can be used [22]. A second approach consists to model only the tail of the probability density of the DIs using the extreme value theory (EVT) [23]. This approach is interesting since it is not necessary to know the whole distribution of the decision statistic in order to develop

a detector. However, it is necessary to have very large databases in order to accurately estimate decision threshold that corresponds to a given PFA.

Figure 6: Probabilistic detection for

In this study, we used several classical indices as those described in the Table 1 and we model the tail of the decision statistics using the whole distribution by means of Parzen windows in order to determine the decision threshold corresponding to a given PFA. This methodology has been applied in our context of composite aircraft nacelles for different configurations of learning sample size. We also compare this method to a more sophisticated one based on the Peaks Over Threshold method extracted from the Extreme Value Theory (see [8] for more details).

Table 1: Different damage indices for two measured signals: healthy, $X(t)$, and unknown, $Y(t)$

DI	Comments
$DI_{CC} = 1 - \rho(X(t), Y(t))$	Cross-correlation ρ is the correlation coefficient
$DI_{MA} = \frac{\max(X(t) - Y(t))}{\max(X(t))}$	Maximum amplitude
$DI_{ENV} = \sqrt{\frac{(\int_0^T (ENV[\delta](t))^2 dt)}{\int_0^T (ENV[x](t))^2 dt}}$	Normalized Envelope ENV is computed with Hilbert transform
$DI_{NRE} = \frac{(X(t) - Y(t))^2}{X(t)^2}$	Normalized residual energy
$DI_{SFT} = \frac{FFT(X(t)Y(t))_{f=f_0}}{FFT(X(t))_{f=f_0}}$	Sliding Window Fourier Transform f_0 is the central excitation frequency

3.2. Probabilistic damage localization

For damage localization, each piezoelectric element attached to the structure acts as an actuator while the others are used as sensors. Performing the difference between signals recorded in healthy and damaged states, a scattered signal containing information related to the damage (location, size, orientation, type) is obtained [13]. Time-of-flight (ToF), which corresponds to the time taken by the wave packet to travel from an actuator to a sensor through a given path, is a feature extracted from the scattered signal that is widely used for damage localization. Knowing the ToF values and the wave velocity, the damage localization problem becomes straightforward: solve a set of deterministic nonlinear equations that describe the relationship between the coordinates of the damage, the ToF, and the wave velocity. Two kinds of equations can be used to do so: those relying on time-of-arrival (ToA) and provide damage location as the intersection of several ellipses and others based on time-difference-of-arrival (TDoA) and provide damage location as the intersection of hyperbolas. Modeling Lamb wave

propagation in isotropic composite plates at a given frequency is relatively simple as only a direction independent group velocity is involved. However, for composite anisotropic plate-like structures, such a model is much more complicated to establish. Indeed, in case of anisotropic plates the wave velocity is now a function of the propagation angle and not a single value [24]. Several techniques have been proposed to overcome this difficulty among them the Bayesian approach proposed by [25].

The proposed localization algorithm is a generalization to anisotropic composite structures of the one proposed by [25]. It's a probabilistic formulation of the ellipses and hyperbola methods and takes into account the uncertainties from ToF measurements. These uncertainties are modeled and then a Bayesian approach is applied to update the posterior distributions of the damage location coordinate. The outstanding of this approach is that it provides both point and confidence interval of the damage location rather than just a single intersection point obtained using deterministic approaches. The damage coordinates are estimated thanks to simulations using a Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) method.

Figure 7, shows the effect of anisotropy on the localization algorithm and Figure 8 an experimental result of localization with its confidence interval.

Figure 7: Numerical Simulation on the composite functional plate (Figure 2) of the effect of anisotropy on the localization algorithm. (a) with the isotropic profile. (b) with the proposed parametrized profile

Figure 8: Experimental results of the Bayesian localization (b) on the composite plate with 14 mm impact coordinates of the impact (300,150)mm and it C-scan (a)

3.3. Temperature compensation

One of the fundamental problems that one face when implementing a SHM Lamb waves based system is to be robust to changes in environmental or operational conditions (EOC). Indeed, variations in EOC such as temperature causes change in instantaneous amplitude and instantaneous phase in signal, thus signal stretching can be observed. Therefore, even in the absence of damage, the signals measured on the same structure at different temperatures exhibit discrepancies; because of the temperature dependence of the mechanical properties of the structure and the performances of the used active elements. The non-temperature compensation during damage detection and localization steps generally

results in a high rate of false alarms. To cope with this problem, several approaches have been used. The most widely ones include optimal baseline selection (OBS) [26] and baseline signal stretch (BaSS) [27].

Figure 9: Illustration of temperature effect on a measured guided waves

A specific Bayesian temperature compensation strategy for composite materials has been developed [28]. The approach considers exact representation of the sensor signal through its Hilbert transform, and the Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) algorithm is used for parameter estimation. The compensation methodology consists of two steps: first, the instantaneous amplitude and the instantaneous phase of the signals are extracted using Hilbert transform, after we apply a Bayesian system identification approach to the temperature compensation problem using the measured piezo-sensor signals at two different temperatures, one considered as reference. After estimating the unknown parameters at each temperature in the operating range, we draw a regression model for these parameters using a weighted least squares method, where the weighting factors are related to the variance obtained via the MCMC procedure. Experimental results on the damaged composite plate of Figure 8a, when the localization algorithm is performed at a temperature that is different from the baseline one are given in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Damage imaging of the composite laminate at two different temperatures with and without temperature compensation: Black circle represents true damage location and red zone the most likely damaged one given by the localization algorithms.

4. APPLICATION TO SUBSTRUCTURES

The part of the nacelle we are interested in is the fan cowl. (see Figure 11a). This structure is geometrically complex and is made of composite monolithic carbon epoxy. The structure is 2.20 m in height for a semi-circumference of 5.80 m. A network of 30 piezoelectric elements used as actuators and sensors has been bonded to the surface of the fan cowl and is used to emit and collect signals. The PZT elements used are numbered from 1 to 30 and mounted at specific positions on the composite plate's surface as shown in Figure 11a. The PZT elements have a diameter of 20 mm, a thickness of 0.1 mm and have been manufactured by Noliac. Several types of damage (Figure 11c) and at different

locations have been considered. The proposed SHM strategy is based on monitoring the structure by zones or cluster (Figure 11b). A result of an impact damage localization is given in Figure 11d where the contour represents the estimated damage location.

Figure 11: (a) Overview of the nacelle fan cowl with the PZT elements and some damage locations (D_i). (b) Monitoring strategy by clusters. (c) A zoom on an impact damage D_1 and its Bayesian localization (d).

5. FLIGHT TESTS RESULTS

A nacelle of an A380 Airbus has been equipped with PZT elements and temperature sensors. Ground measurements have been recorded after each mission of the aircraft. The missions have been performed in different operational conditions. We present below (Figure 12) the results of the temperature compensation algorithm when applied to the assessment of the in-service nacelle fan cowl. As it can be seen, the algorithm allows to correct discrepancies introduced by temperature and hence enhance damage detection and localization.

Figure 12 : Effect of temperature compensation algorithm on in-service nacelle fan cowl measurements.

6. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have presented the complete process of an embedded structural health monitoring (SHM) system enabling condition-based maintenance of aircraft nacelles. It describes the complete process from the choice of the active elements to the implementation of the SHM strategy by means of elastic waves on an A380 nacelle and analysis of the results.

We first describe a validation procedure of piezoelectric elements bonding on composite structures with respects to the host-structures operational environment. Then a Bayesian framework has been

considered taking into account for the facts that experimental ToFs are corrupted by noise and variability due to anisotropy of composite materials and changes in environmental or operational conditions.

The SHM process has been validated on functional and substructures (with actual scale) before carrying out flight tests on an A380. The recorded flight data are still being processed and results will be further outlined in forthcoming publications.

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7. BIBLIOGRAPHIE

- [1] W. J. Staszewski, C. Boller, and G. R. Tomlinson, *Health monitoring of aerospace structures: smart sensor technologies and signal processing*.: John Wiley and Sons, 2004.
- [2] R. Hajrya and N. Mechbal, "Principal Component Analysis and Perturbation Theory Based Robust Damage Detection of Multifunctional Aircraft Structure," *Structural Health Monitoring an International Journal*, 2013.
- [3] F.-K. Chang, "Structural Health Monitoring: Condition-based Maintenance," in *8th International Workshop on Structural Health Monitoring (IWSHM)*, Stanford, 2011.
- [4] K. Worden, C. R. Farrar, G. Manson, and G., Park, "The fundamental axioms of structural health monitoring.," *Proceeding of the Royal Society*, vol. 463, pp. 1639-1664, 2007.
- [5] Su Zhongqing, Ye Lin, and Lu Ye, "Guided Lamb waves for identification of damage in composite structures: A review," *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, vol. 295, pp. 753-780, 2006.
- [6] C. Fendzi et al., "Optimal Sensors Placement to Enhance Damage Detection in Composite Plates," in *EWSHM*, Nantes, France., 2014.
- [7] C. Fendzi, N. Mechbal, M. Rebillat, and M. Guskov, "A General Bayesian Framework for Ellipse-based and Hyperbola-based Damage Localisation in Anisotropic Composite Plates," *Journal of Intelligent Material Systems and Structures*, vol. 27, no. 3, pp. 350-374, 2016,
- [8] M. Rebillat, O. Hmad, F. Kadri, and N. Mechbal, "Peaks Over Threshold Based Detector Design for Structural Health Monitoring: application to aerospace structures," *Structural Health Monitoring an international journal*, 2017.
- [9] G. Park, C. R. Farrar, A. C. Rutherford, and A. N. Robertson, "Piezoelectric active sensor self-diagnostics using electrical admittance measurements," *Journal of Vibration and Acoustics-transactions of the ASME*, vol. 128, pp. 469-476, 2006.
- [10] G. Park, C. R. Farrar, F. L. di Scalea, and S. Coccia, "Performance assessment and validation of piezoelectric active-sensors in structural health monitoring," *Smart Materials & Structures*, vol. 15, pp. 1673-1683, 2006.
- [11] S. Park, G. Park, C. B. Yun, and C. R. Farrar, "Sensor Self-diagnosis Using a Modified Impedance Model for Active Sensing-based Structural Health Monitoring," *Structural Health Monitoring-an International Journal*, vol. 8, pp. 71-82, 2009.
- [12] T. G. Overly, G. Park, K. M. Farinholt, and C. R. Farrar, "Piezoelectric Active-Sensor Diagnostics and Validation Using Instantaneous Baseline Data," *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 9, pp. 1414-1421, 2009.
- [13] V. Giurgiutiu and A. N. Zagrai, "Embedded self-sensing piezoelectric active sensors for on-line structural identification," *Journal of Vibration and Acoustics-transactions of the ASME*, vol. 124, pp. 116-125, 2002.
- [14] B. L. Grisso and D. J. Inman, "Temperature corrected sensor diagnostics for impedance-based SHM," *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, vol. 329, pp. 2323-2336, 2009.
- [15] S. G. Taylor, G. Park, K. M. Farinholt, and M. D. Todd, "Diagnostics for piezoelectric transducers under cyclic loads deployed for structural health monitoring applications," *Smart Materials and Structures*, vol. 22, 2013.

- [16] Y. Zheng, C. Martinez, D. Easton, G. Park, and K. Farinholt, "Sensor Self-Diagnostics for Piezoelectric Transducers Operating in Harsh Temperature Environments," in *Proceedings of SPIE Smart Structures and Materials & Nondestructive Evaluation and Health Monitoring Conference*, San Diego CA, 2011.
- [17] J. L. Blackshire and A. T. Cooney, "Characterization of bonded piezoelectric sensor performance and durability in simulated aircraft environments," *Review of Progress in Quantitative Nondestructive Evaluation*, vol. 25, pp. 1694-1701, 2006.
- [18] S. Chesné and A. Deraemaeker, "Damage localization using transmissibility functions: A critical review," *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing*, vol. 38, pp. 569–584, 2013.
- [19] K. Saeed, N. Mechbal, G. Coffignal, and M. Vergé, "Artificial Neural Network Based Structural Damage Diagnosis Using Nonparametric Subspace Residual," in *7th International Workshop on Structural Health Monitoring, IWSHM*, Stanford (USA), 2009.
- [20] Y. Liu, N. Mechbal, and M. Vergé, "Damage monitoring based on wave illumination of structures," in *International Workshop on Structural Health Monitoring (IWSHM)*, Stanford, USA, 2011.
- [21] O. Hmad, C. Fendzi, N. Mechbal, and M. Rebillat, "Verification and Validation of Structural Health Monitoring Algorithms: A Maturation Procedure.," in *9th IFAC Symposium SAFEPROCESS'15*, Paris, 2015.
- [22] O. Hmad, J-R. Masse, E. Grall-Maes, P. Beuseroy, and A. Mathevet, "Maturation of Detection Functions by Performances Benchmark. Application to a PHM Algorithm," *CHEMICAL ENGINEERING*, vol. 33, 2013.
- [23] S. Coles, *An Introduction to Statistical Modeling of Extreme Values*. London: Springer-Verlag, 2001.
- [24] J. Harley and J. Moura, "Scale transform signal processing for optimal ultrasonic temperature compensation.," *Ultrasonics, Ferroelectrics and Frequency Control, IEEE Transactions on*, vol. 59, no. 10, 2012.
- [25] G. Yan, "A Bayesian approach for damage localization in plate-like structures using Lamb waves," *Smart Mater. Struct.*, vol. 22, p. 035012, 2013.
- [26] G. Konstantinidis, B. Drinkwater, and P. Wilcox, "The temperature stability of guided wave structural health monitoring systems.," *Smart Materials and Structures*, vol. 15, no. 4, p. 967, 2006.
- [27] J. Harley and J. Moura, "Scale transform signal processing for optimal ultrasonic temperature compensation.," *Ultrasonics, Ferroelectrics and Frequency Control, IEEE Transaction on*, vol. 59, no. 10, 2012.
- [28] C. Fendzi, M. Rébillat, N. Mechbal, M. Guskov, and G. Coffignal, "A Bayesian-Based Temperature Compensation Approach for Structural Health Monitoring using Lamb Waves," *Structural Health Monitoring*, vol. 15, no. 5, pp. 525-540, 2016b, to appear.